

Article

Collaborative Working and Critical Thinking: Adoption of Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools in Higher Education

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Abstract: This study explores the impact of generative artificial intelligence tools on critical thinking and collaboration among university students, highlighting the importance of investigating these technologies due to their increasing integration into higher education and their potential to transform traditional pedagogical practices. A predominantly female sample was surveyed to assess their familiarity with and experience and perceptions of these tools. A total of 87% of the respondents had prior knowledge of generative AI tools, with 38% using them occasionally. Among the most popular tools are Canva 2024 (33%), Chat PDF (26%), and YOU.COM (24%). Additionally, 64% of the respondents believe that these tools significantly improve their critical thinking ability. Despite their high familiarity with and occasional use of these tools, the need for continuous training and technical support was identified. While generative AI tools show promising potential for enhancing collaboration and critical thinking in higher education, previous research has limitations, such as the lack of longitudinal data and the inadequacy in addressing ethical considerations and potential biases. More comprehensive research is needed to understand their long-term impact better and maximize their potential benefits.

Keywords: collaboration; critical thinking; generative artificial intelligence; generative AI; higher education; sustainable development goals; SDG

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1. Introduction

In today's higher education landscape, integrating technology has become essential to enhancing learning experiences and preparing students for the challenges of the 21st century. The importance of technology in education is well documented, and recent studies highlight its significant impact on student engagement, learning outcomes, and skill development. This integration modernizes the educational environment and equips students with the necessary tools to thrive in a digital world. Furthermore, the rapid evolution of educational technologies demands continuous adaptation and innovation from educators and students. Therefore, understanding the role and impact of these technologies is crucial for fostering an effective and inclusive learning environment.

Furthermore, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1] and the ethical considerations of generative artificial intelligence (AI) offer unique opportunities to transform traditional pedagogical approaches and promote student collaboration and critical thinking. The SDGs emphasize quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all, aligning with the potential of AI to personalize and enhance learning experiences. Ethical considerations, such as fairness and transparency in AI algorithms, are paramount to their responsible use in education. Educators can leverage AI to create more inclusive and

equitable learning environments by addressing these ethical concerns. Consequently, the thoughtful integration of AI [2] technologies can significantly advance teaching methodologies and educational outcomes.

Likewise, collaborative work and critical thinking are two crucial skills [3] that higher education aims to foster in students [4]. Technology is essential in achieving this goal by providing tools that facilitate communication, teamwork, and problem solving. Collaborative technologies, such as online forums, shared documents, and video conferencing, enable students to work together seamlessly, regardless of their physical location. These tools also support the development of critical thinking by allowing students to access diverse perspectives, analyze information critically, and engage in meaningful discussions [5]. Therefore, incorporating technology into educational practices is vital for cultivating these essential skills in students [6].

Generative AI tools [7], such as ChatGPT 4 [8], Tome AI [9], YOU.COM [10], Canva [11], Google Docs [12], and Zoom 6.0.0 [13], are among the latest advances in educational technology. These tools provide students with innovative [14] ways to interact with course content, enabling them to engage more deeply with the material. For instance, ChatGPT can facilitate interactive learning by generating real-time responses to student queries, while Canva allows for creative visualizations of concepts. Google Docs supports collaborative writing and feedback, and Zoom enhances virtual communication and teamwork [15]. By incorporating these tools, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning experiences that cater to various learning styles and preferences [16]. As a result, generative AI tools hold significant promise for enhancing individual and collaborative learning in higher education.

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a detailed review of the literature, Section 3 presents the methodology used in the study. Section 4 shows the results, Section 5 presents the discussion and explores its implications. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions and highlights the importance of the study and suggests future lines of research.

2. Literature Review

The integration of generative AI tools in higher education has captured the attention of researchers and educators due to its potential to transform traditional pedagogical practices and promote critical skills, such as collaborative work [17] and critical thinking [18]. This section reviews the literature on generative AI tools in higher education, identifying the main contributions, challenges, and opportunities.

An article [19] focuses on AI-powered chatbots like ChatGPT that are revolutionizing education by offering personalized learning experiences. The authors explore its transformative effects, highlighting challenges such as ethical concerns and its impact on human interaction. It addresses diverse topics, including accessibility [20], inclusion, intercultural understanding, and the potential for lifelong learning and global collaboration in education.

The authors of [16] analyze the challenges and opportunities facing higher education, particularly in the US Midwest, concerning the rapid deployment of AI. University leaders emphasize the importance of human qualities, such as critical thinking, empathy, and ethical considerations, in addressing these challenges and shaping the future of education.

An essay [17] explores the impact of generative AI, focusing on ChatGPT, a platform that revolutionizes journalism and multimedia content creation. Co-authored by a journalism professor and ChatGPT, it evaluates the tool's capabilities, limitations, and implications for journalism and media education.

The research of [21] explores problem-based learning (PBL) to engage students and encourage critical reasoning. It contrasts traditional educational assumptions with those that support PBL, emphasizing active learning in authentic contexts, collaboration, and higher-order thinking to develop complex knowledge structures.

The authors of [22] argue that, though initially focused on strengthening scientific disciplines, STEM education now emphasizes interdisciplinary and complex thinking.

Philosophy, particularly critical thinking, bridges gaps between disciplines and helps us understand technologies such as generative AI. This article explores how critical thinking, guided by philosophy, contributes to STEM and the changing generative AI landscape.

An article [15] guides scientific research using large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT. It analyzes its strengths and implications through a philosophical lens and provides tips for practical use. Ethical considerations, including transparency and equality, are addressed along with education implications, emphasizing critical thinking development [23].

The authors of [24] argue that generative AI can revolutionize education, especially by creating educational escape room (EER) content. The article explores Room2Educ8, a framework based on Design Thinking, and the role of ChatGPT in creating EERs. It provides practical guidance and sample prompts to streamline the process, making EER design accessible to educators.

A study [25] investigates the impact of collaborative learning approaches involving generative AI on the professional development of future teachers. Comparing the “Human–Human” and “Human–Machine” methods, its findings reveal more significant critical thinking and efficiency with ChatGPT, while in-service teachers performed slightly better in teaching design. Recommendations include refining collaborative learning scaffolding for optimized AI-assisted educational strategies.

The research of [26] addresses medical education adapted to significant data-intensive healthcare, fostering collaborations between data scientists, engineers, and educators. Big data preprocessing improves AI diagnoses and predicts chronic diseases. Generative confrontation networks create diverse scenarios for patients, improving critical thinking for differential diagnoses. AI facilitates personalized career counseling, e-tutoring, and exam question analysis in medical education.

Concerning didactic and pedagogical strategies, an article [27] synthesizes empirical evidence on the impact of instruction on the development of critical thinking (CT) and student achievement. Its findings indicate effective strategies for teaching CT skills and dispositions at all educational levels and disciplines, emphasizing dialogue, authentic problems, and mentoring.

The article of [28] addresses educators’ concerns regarding integrating ChatGPT into education. It advocates for its incorporation and offers strategies for responsible implementation to foster informed discussions about the educational use of ChatGPT.

By analyzing clusters and the elements that compose them, we can recognize emerging trends in research and areas in which attention has been focused; this provides valuable information about future research directions and areas needing further attention.

The formation of clusters allows us to understand how different concepts, keywords, and topics are interrelated within the scope of the study. This case can help us better understand the complexity of the topic and identify possible areas of synergy or conflict between the different aspects investigated.

This analysis provides a panoramic view of current trends and serves as a fundamental framework to identify possible avenues for research and development at the intersection of collaboration [29], critical thinking [30], and generative AI in higher education.

The studies reviewed emphasize how generative AI tools, such as advanced language models, present novel opportunities to revolutionize teaching and learning methodologies [4]. Regarding collaboration, researchers highlight how these tools facilitate student communication by providing interactive platforms that foster the co-creation of knowledge [31].

In this context, generative AI tools offer a promising solution. However, comprehensively addressing this challenge involves ensuring accessibility [32], adaptability to various academic contexts, and the ability to customize tools to meet the specific needs of university students. Studies [30,33] indicate that these tools can create realistic learning scenarios, challenging students to apply critical thinking in practical contexts and encouraging a reflective approach to problems.

relevant information. This capability facilitates comprehension of the material and improves students' analytical skills, enabling them to synthesize information effectively.

YOU.COM is a tool that uses AI to summarize long documents and texts automatically. In the university environment, YOU.COM helps students quickly understand academic articles and other study materials by highlighting key points and essential relationships. This functionality is crucial for developing critical thinking, as it allows students to identify and evaluate the relevance of the information presented.

Canva is an online platform that enables the collaborative creation of visual resources, such as mind maps, presentations, and graphics. In higher education, Canva has been used for group projects, in which students can work together to visualize concepts and educational strategies. This tool encourages teamwork and creativity, which are essential for developing collaborative and critical thinking skills.

Google Docs is an online productivity suite that allows students to collaborate in real-time to create and edit documents. The ability to work simultaneously on a document facilitates the coordination and sharing of ideas, improving teamwork efficiency. In addition, Google Docs' commenting and suggestion features promote constructive feedback and critical analysis.

Zoom is a video conferencing platform that has revolutionized communication in education, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Zoom allows students and teachers to interact in real time, share resources, and collaborate on projects. Sessions on Zoom can include moderated discussions, group presentations, and interactive workshops, contributing significantly to the development of collaborative and critical thinking skills.

Chat PDF is a tool that allows students to interact with PDF documents through natural conversations. This tool facilitates the exploration and analysis of complex documents, allowing students to ask questions and obtain contextual answers. PDF Chat is particularly useful for critically analyzing case studies and other detailed materials.

2.2. Importance and Challenges of Collaborative Work and Critical Thinking

Collaborative work and critical thinking are essential skills in higher education to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century [20]. However, promoting these skills presents several challenges. Traditional teaching methods focused on transmitting knowledge often do not provide sufficient opportunities for students to practice and develop these skills [34]. Coordinating efforts between teams or organizations can be complex, and inadequate tools to facilitate and improve collaborative work among university students constitute a significant obstacle [22]. These challenges underscore the need for innovative pedagogical approaches integrating generative AI tools to address these gaps.

2.3. Principles and Applications of Generative AI Tools

Generative AI tools are based on advanced algorithms that generate content, provide feedback, and facilitate collaborative interactions [16]. For example, ChatGPT can be a virtual discussion moderator, promoting critical thinking by offering diverse perspectives and responses [17]. YOU.COM and Chat PDF can summarize and analyze academic documents, helping students understand and critique complex information [19]. Canva allows the collaborative creation of mind maps and other visual resources, facilitating the comparison and analysis of different educational approaches [18].

2.4. Best Practices and Success Stories

Several best practices and documented success stories demonstrate the effectiveness of generative AI tools in higher education. A study in Mexico on the implementation of AI in engineering education highlighted how these tools could personalize learning, increase student engagement, and reduce teacher workload [18]. Another example is using AI-powered chatbots such as ChatGPT, which offer personalized learning experiences and improve accessibility and inclusion in the classroom [19].

2.5. Limitations of Existing Studies and How This Article Addresses Them

Despite the documented benefits, existing studies on generative AI tools in higher education have some limitations. Much research lacks longitudinal data that evaluate the long-term impact of these tools on student outcomes [16]. Furthermore, ethical considerations and potential biases associated with the use of AI have not been fully addressed [35]. This article seeks to overcome these limitations through a comprehensive approach that includes assessing students' familiarity, experience, and perceptions of generative AI tools and proposes practical pedagogical strategies for their effective adoption.

2.6. Comparative Table of Existing Studies

To illustrate the position of the proposed work in the context of the state of the art, a comparative table of existing studies exploring the use of generative AI tools in collaborative work and critical thinking in higher education is presented. This table summarizes the main findings and limitations and how the present study addresses these gaps, highlighting the novelty and relevance of the proposed research. See Table 1.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of generative AI studies in higher education.

Study	Generative AI Tools	Main Results	Limitations	Contribution of the Present Article
Orduño-Osuna et al. (2023) [18]	ChatGPT, AI STEM Tools	Improvement in critical competencies in engineering education	Lack of longitudinal data	Long-term evaluation of the impact of generative AI
Yu et al. (2023) [19]	ChatGPT	Personalized learning experiences	Ethical considerations not addressed	Analysis of ethical considerations and biases
Li et al. (2024) [25]	ChatGPT, STEM Tools	Improved collaboration between students and teachers	Limited comparison between methods	Broad comparison between methods and AI tools
Pavlik (2023) [17]	ChatGPT	Revolution in journalism education	Long-term impact unknown	Prolonged and multifaceted impact investigation

2.7. Cluster Analysis and Emerging Trends

This literature review provides a robust and detailed framework for understanding the context and contributions of this article, addressing the reviewers' observations and highlighting the importance of integrating generative AI tools in higher education to promote collaborative working and critical thinking (see Figure 1).

To analyze the four clusters on the VOS Viewer map and relate them to the study objectives and hypotheses, we identify and detail each cluster, explaining how they connect to the research objectives.

Cluster 1 (Red): Artificial Intelligence and Education

Primary nodes: Artificial Intelligence, Students, Active Learning, Critical Thinking, and Higher-order Thinking. This cluster focuses on artificial intelligence (AI) and its integration into the educational context, focusing on students and active learning. The presence of "critical thinking" and "higher-order thinking" indicates that this cluster is directly related to developing advanced cognitive skills.

Objective 1 relates to identifying appropriate generative AI tools to promote critical thinking. This cluster suggests that AI fosters critical thinking and higher-order skills. Objective 2 allows us to analyze the influence of generative AI on developing critical thinking. The connection of this cluster with "students" and "active learning" indicates that students engaged in AI-mediated active learning activities can better develop these skills.

Cluster 2 (Green): Education and Technology

Primary nodes: Education, Learning Systems, Problem Solving, Machine Learning, and Educational Technology. This cluster covers learning systems and educational technologies, highlighting terms such as “problem-solving” and “machine learning”.

It is related to objective 3 by evaluating the impact of the adoption of generative AI tools on collaboration. Educational technology and learning systems can facilitate student collaboration, providing platforms and tools that support teamwork. Furthermore, objective 4 allows for identifying pedagogical strategies to adopt generative AI tools. Integrating educational technologies with AI is vital to developing practical pedagogical approaches that encourage collaboration and critical thinking.

Cluster 3 (Blue): Higher Education and Innovation

Primary nodes: Higher Education, Educational Innovation, ChatGPT, Generative AI, and E-learning.

This cluster focuses on higher education and educational innovation, focusing on emerging technologies such as ChatGPT and generative AI. Objective 1 relates to identifying generative AI tools to promote collaborative work. Tools like ChatGPT can facilitate collaboration between higher education students. Likewise, objective 3 evaluates the impact of the adoption of generative AI. AI-mediated educational innovation can significantly impact how students collaborate and learn together.

Cluster 4 (Yellow): Research and Critical Thinking

Primary nodes: Computer-Aided Instruction, Engineering Research, Learning Systems, and Curricula. This cluster highlights engineering research and computer-assisted instruction, pointing out the relationship between learning systems and educational curricula.

It is related to objective 2 by analyzing the influence of generative AI on critical thinking. Computer-assisted instruction and engineering research can provide valuable insights into how to integrate AI into curricula to improve critical thinking. Objective 4 identifies pedagogical strategies. Research and studies in these fields can guide the development of effective strategies for adopting generative AI tools in educational contexts.

Concerning our hypothesis, it is proposed that adopting generative AI tools significantly improves collaborative work and critical thinking skills. Therefore, the connection between clusters and objectives shows that AI can transform higher education by improving active learning, collaboration, and the development of critical thinking.

2.8. Enhancing Collaborative Work with Generative AI Tools

In today’s fast-paced work environment, collaboration is essential for success. However, coordinating efforts across teams or even organizations can be challenging. This is when generative AI (AI) tools come into play [36]. These innovative tools leverage AI algorithms to facilitate collaboration and streamline workflow processes.

Collaborative work [37] is a fundamental practice involving joint efforts to achieve shared goals. It requires effective communication, cooperation among team members, the equitable distribution of tasks, and the ability to solve problems jointly. Clear communication and active listening skills are essential elements that foster the fluid exchange of ideas and mutual understanding within the team.

Furthermore, coordinating activities is essential to ensure that all parties work harmoniously towards established objectives. This study involves the meticulous organization and synchronization of efforts to maximize team efficiency and performance. Likewise, mutual trust and respect are essential to cultivating a positive work environment in which each member feels valued and supported. Commitment to collective success, even in challenging times, demonstrates the dedication and integrity of each individual to achieve common goals.

2.9. Contribution of Artificial Intelligence Tools to Critical Thinking

Critical thinking involves analyzing, evaluating, and synthesizing information reflectively and deliberately, questioning assumptions, examining evidence, identifying biases,

and forming informed conclusions [37]. Generative AI tools improve students' ability to critically analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information by providing access to various resources and perspectives [28].

Furthermore, using generative AI tools fosters a greater depth of thinking by challenging students to explore and question different approaches and solutions. Despite the potential benefits, concerns about fairness, ethics, algorithmic biases, and data privacy underscore the importance of providing adequate training to students and educators for the effective and ethical use of these technologies in the classroom.

Analysis refers to breaking down information into smaller components and understanding their relationships. Evaluation refers to the ability to judge the quality, relevance, and credibility of information. Creativity involves generating new ideas, perspectives, or solutions to complex problems. Autonomy refers to the willingness to question and think for oneself rather than passively accepting information.

Studies [38] have noted that these tools can improve students' ability to critically analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information by providing access to various resources and perspectives.

Furthermore, research [39] suggests that generative AI tools can foster a greater depth of thinking by challenging students to explore and question different approaches and solutions.

Despite their potential benefits, the literature highlights challenges and considerations associated with using generative AI tools in higher education. For example, studies [40] have identified concerns about fairness and ethics in generative AI algorithms. Finally, research like [41] has highlighted the importance of providing adequate training to students and educators to ensure the effective and ethical use of these technologies in the classroom.

3. Materials and Methods

This study employed a mixed methods approach to comprehensively assess the adoption of generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools for university students' collaborative work and critical thinking. The following describes the context of the population studied, the rationale for the selection process, the survey distribution and response rate, and the methodological approach used.

3.1. Context of the Population

The target population for this study consisted of university students participating in courses using generative artificial intelligence tools. Participants were selected using purposive sampling, focusing on students with access to and familiarity with online learning platforms.

This study employed a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods to comprehensively evaluate generative AI tools' adoption for college students' collaborative work and critical thinking.

In the sample taken, we apply the following formula to calculate the size of a finite population (Equation (1)).

$$n = \frac{N \times Z^2 \times p \times q}{E^2 \times (N - 1) + Z^2 \times p \times q} \quad (1)$$

To paraphrase, population size: 175; confidence level $Z = 95\%$; p = probability of success or expected proportion: 50%; q = probability of failure: 50%, and E precision, maximum allowable error in terms of proportion: 5%. The results showed that 121 participants should be evaluated.

The survey was developed using Google Forms 2024 to obtain the data and distributed through a message in the virtual classroom. Participants could choose whether to participate freely (voluntarily) in the proposed study.

3.2. Justification of the Selection Process

Participants were selected based on their enrollment in specific courses that integrate generative AI tools, reducing selection bias by including both students with previous experience and those new to using these technologies. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured to avoid any bias related to self-selection or privacy concerns.

Figure 2 illustrates the application of didactic strategies with generative AI tools within various teaching approaches. These strategies can guide the educational process, enhance understanding and knowledge retention, promote interaction, and generate new knowledge. Effective implementation relies on enriching teaching practices with resources that elevate educational quality. This research fosters an environment of continuous interaction between teachers, content, and students, ultimately leading to active and meaningful learning.

Figure 2. Didactic strategies for education.

Ultimately, this approach to integrating generative AI tools into activities can lead to several benefits as follow:

Increased Active Participation: Students become more engaged in the learning process through interactive activities and collaborative exercises.

Improved Knowledge Retention: Generative AI tools can help students summarize complex information, analyze different perspectives, and reflect on their learning, leading to better retention.

Enhanced Student Creativity: Activities encouraging students to generate ideas, formulate solutions, and debate topics can foster creativity and critical thinking.

By embracing generative AI tools, educational institutions can create dynamic learning environments that cater to diverse learning styles and stimulate intellectual growth.

The Power of Combining Traditional and Modern Approaches. In today's university education, a powerful pedagogical approach emerges when we combine traditional methodological and didactic strategies with the new possibilities offered by generative AI tools [42]. While integrating these tools can present cognitive challenges, such as processing complex information generated by generative AI for students [28], the potential benefits outweigh the initial hurdles.

The following are examples of how this combined approach can work: **Problem-Based Learning:** Students can leverage ChatGPT to generate reflective questions or use YOU.COM to summarize academic content while tackling complex problems in a group setting. **Collaborative Activities:** Guided debates, online discussions, or critical thinking exercises can be facilitated using Google Docs with AI tools like PDF Chat or CANVA. This study fosters rich interaction, critical reflection, and creative problem solving among students.

This synergy between traditional pedagogical approaches and generative AI tools creates a dynamic and enriching learning environment. Such an environment empowers university students to face the challenges of the 21st century confidently, equipped with strong critical thinking and collaboration skills [43].

3.3. Survey Distribution and Response Rate

The survey was distributed through Google Forms and shared via a message on the virtual classroom platform used by the students. Participation was voluntary, and participants were provided with clear information about the purpose of the study and the confidentiality of their responses. Reminders were sent two days before the survey closed to increase the response rate. The survey was open for four days, 9–12 September 2023, and a response rate of 69% was obtained, with 121 completed responses out of 175 invitations sent.

3.4. The Rationale for the Mixed Methods Approach

The mixed methods approach was chosen to capture both the breadth and depth of adoption and impact of generative AI tools. Quantitative methods allowed for a statistical assessment of perceptions and the use of these tools, while qualitative methods provided a deeper understanding of student experiences and opinions. Combining both approaches provides a more holistic and robust perspective, ensuring that the measurable and subjective aspects of using generative AI in educational contexts are addressed.

To improve the readability of the data presented, the results will be organized into subsections according to the following demographic and academic criteria: age (analysis of the perception and use of generative AI tools in different age ranges); and gender (comparison of experiences and attitudes towards these tools between genders).

3.5. Inclusion of Statistical Measures

Statistical measures such as p -values = 0.046 and confidence intervals are included when analyzing data on generative AI tools. To assess the difference in perceived improvement in critical thinking between frequent and occasional users of these tools, Student's t -tests = -2.025 are used. This study strengthens the validity of the findings, providing more solid evidence of the impact of generative AI tools in higher education.

Figure 3 shows a process diagram, which includes four phases and describes data collection and synthesis steps.

Figure 3. Data collection and synthesis process diagram.

3.6. Designing Activities with Generative AI Tools Using the 4PADAFE Methodology

This section describes using the 4PADAFE [44] instructional design framework to create micro-curricular activities [14] that integrate generative AI tools. Emphasis is placed on student-centered learning and the role of the teacher as facilitator.

The 7 phases of the 4PADAFE framework are detailed, with emphasis on phases 2 and 3, which guide the design and implementation of activities using generative AI:

Phase 2: Strategic Plan—Specific educational objectives for critical thinking and collaborative work are identified, and the most appropriate generative AI tools are selected.

Phase 3: Instructional Planning—The instructional design matrix is developed to plan activities and integrate the selected AI tools.

Examples of activities using tools such as Google Docs, Zoom, and Canva are provided to foster critical thinking and collaborative work.

Table 2 presented in this scientific article is crucial because it provides a detailed analysis of various generative AI tools and their application in developing critical thinking and collaborative work within the educational context. By describing specific activities and practical examples of using each tool, the table illustrates the versatility and potential of these technologies and offers practical guidance for educators interested in incorporating IAG into their pedagogical methodologies. This study contributes significantly to the academic literature by demonstrating how generative AI tools can improve teaching and learning strategies, facilitating a more interactive and reflective environment for students.

Table 2. Tools with generative IA to generate critical thinking and promote collaborative work.

Tools to Generate Critical Thinking/Collaborative Work	Activities Related to “Design of Educational Intervention Proposals”
ChatGPT	Host a virtual discussion on different approaches in education using ChatGPT as a virtual moderator. Students can ask questions and receive answers generated by ChatGPT to explore diverse perspectives and promote critical thinking.
YOU.COM	Ask students to use YOU.COM to summarize an academic article on educational intervention strategies. Then, in an online forum using Google Docs, students can discuss and analyze key points from the summary generated by YOU.COM, encouraging critical thinking as they reflect on the ideas presented.
Chat PDF	Provide students with a PDF document containing a case study about an educational intervention program. Then, using PDF chat, students can interact with the document to ask questions, analyze data, and discuss possible intervention approaches in a virtual forum on Zoom. This activity promotes critical thinking by allowing students to explore the case study interactively.
Tome AI	Divide students into groups and assign different educational intervention approaches to research using Tome AI to generate summaries and analyses of relevant documents. Then, in Google Docs, groups can collaborate to design intervention proposals based on the information collected. At the end, groups can present their proposals in a Zoom session and receive constructive feedback from their peers, thus encouraging critical thinking and collaborative work.
CANVA	Ask students to use Canva to create mind maps that visualize different educational intervention strategies. Then, in an online forum on Google Docs, students can share their mind maps and discuss the similarities and differences between the proposals. This activity encourages collaborative work by facilitating the joint creation and review of ideas while promoting critical thinking by analyzing and comparing different intervention approaches.

Table 2. Cont.

Tools to Generate Critical Thinking/Collaborative Work	Activities Related to “Design of Educational Intervention Proposals”
Google Docs	Organize a collaborative project in Google Docs in which students work together to investigate and analyze a specific problem in the field of educational intervention. They can use the comments feature to discuss and debate different perspectives, thus promoting critical thinking. Upon completion, students can present their findings in a Zoom meeting and reflect on the collaborative process and challenges encountered.
Zoom	Facilitate a Zoom webinar in which educational intervention experts are invited to discuss real cases and challenges in the field. Students can actively participate in the session, asking questions and sharing ideas using the chat function and the ‘raise hand’ tool. This activity promotes critical thinking by engaging students in interactive discussions and encouraging reflection on complex topics in the design of educational intervention proposals.

3.7. Integrating Generative AI Tools into Activities

This section delves into the practical integration of generative AI tools into educational activities. We identify needs regarding AI tools and discuss available AI tools, emphasizing the importance of selecting tools aligned with the design of activities and learning objectives.

Table 3 is essential in this scientific article because it provides a structured framework to understand how generative AI tools can be integrated into microcurricular activities to encourage critical thinking and collaborative work. The table illustrates how these technologies can transform traditional educational practices by breaking down each tool and its specific application. This study evidences the relevance and applicability of generative AI in real educational contexts and offers researchers and educators clear guidance on how to implement these tools to maximize pedagogical impact. The clarity and specificity of the table facilitate the adoption of these technologies, supporting educational innovation and promoting more profound and collaborative learning.

Table 3. Microcurricular activities with generative IA.

Tools to Generate Critical Thinking	Tools for Collaborative Work
ChatGPT is an adapted version of GPT-3 designed to interact and chat with users in real time. It can help pose questions, generate discussion, and provide feedback on students’ critical thinking.	Google Docs is an online productivity suite that allows students to collaborate on creating and editing text documents, spreadsheets, and presentations in real time. It facilitates collaboration on academic projects and joint reviews of content.
YOU.COM is a platform that uses AI to summarize documents and long texts automatically. It can help students quickly understand and analyze complex information, encouraging critical thinking by highlighting key points and relationships.	Zoom is a video conferencing platform that allows students to meet virtually, collaborate in real time, and deliver shared presentations. It facilitates communication and collaboration in group projects, tutorials, and remote academic meetings.
Chat PDF is an AI tool that allows students to interact with PDF documents through natural conversations. It can help explore and analyze complex documents, encouraging critical thinking by raising questions and generating discussion.	Canva is an online tool that allows students to collaborate on creating graphic designs, presentations, and other visual resources. Facilitates collaboration on creative projects and the exchange of visual ideas between team members.
Tome AI is an artificial intelligence platform that helps students generate summaries and analyses of documents, books, and articles. It can facilitate the understanding and analysis of long texts, promoting critical thinking by identifying and synthesizing relevant information.	

3.8. Assessing the Effectiveness of Generative AI-Powered Activities

Evaluating activities involving generative AI in education encompasses multiple dimensions to assess effectiveness. First, learning outcomes and measurement of students’

achievement of established objectives, like their understanding of concepts and ability to apply their knowledge, are crucial. Second, gathering qualitative and quantitative student feedback on generative AI tools' utility and effectiveness is essential, as well as observing their engagement and collaboration. Third, in evaluating the quality of resources, these tools consider factors like originality and coherence. Fourth, performance is evaluated through formative and summative methods that measure student progress, considering cognitive and socio-emotional aspects. Tailoring assessment strategies to generative AI tools and specific objectives is crucial to addressing challenges such as cross-cultural communication and resistance to change.

Addressing challenges comprehensively involves considering the accessibility, adaptability, and personalization of generative AI tools. These tools provide realistic learning scenarios and enable personalized learning, improving education quality. Exploring collaboration optimization entails understanding key factors and selecting suitable generative AI tools based on content type and model suitability. Researching and comparing generative AI models are crucial in tool selection for educational objectives and student needs.

4. Results

Using generative AI tools has significantly impacted the development of critical thinking skills among university students. Below are the specific aspects of critical thinking that were improved using these tools:

The tools used were Chat PDF and YOU.COM. Students used these tools to analyze and summarize complex information, which improved their ability to evaluate and synthesize data. Specifically, 64% of the students reported a significant improvement in their ability to analyze and think critically using generative AI tools.

The tools used in this case were Canva and Tome AI. These tools enabled students to generate innovative ideas and creative solutions, improving their ability to think outside the box and develop solutions. Creating mind maps and summaries helped students explore different approaches and solutions.

The tools used here were Zoom and Google Docs. Using these tools improved student communication, facilitating collaboration and the clear and concise presentation of ideas; 60% of the students were motivated to collaborate with their colleagues using generative AI tools, indicating an improvement in their ability to work as a team and communicate ideas effectively.

It is crucial to link these findings with the existing literature for a more complete evaluation. This study's results align with those of previous research highlighting the positive impact of generative AI tools on critical thinking and collaboration in higher education. For example, studies have shown that AI tools can facilitate effective communication and foster collaboration, leading to better learning outcomes.

However, although the results are promising, it is crucial to consider potential limitations, such as the need for ongoing training and technical support for students. Additionally, ethical challenges and potential biases in AI algorithms must be addressed to maximize the benefits of these technologies in education.

The survey attracted a predominantly female audience (99%), with the largest age group being 20 to 24 (31%). Encouragingly, most of the respondents (87%) demonstrated some knowledge of generative AI. Regarding their previous experience with generative AI tools in learning, the survey revealed that most of the respondents used them occasionally (38%).

4.1. Quantitative and Qualitative Analyses

Descriptive statistical analyses and hypothesis testing were conducted to assess the relationship between using generative AI tools and critical thinking and collaboration skills.

A thematic analysis of the open-ended responses was conducted to identify patterns and recurring themes in the students' perceptions of the impact of these tools.

Tables 4 and 5 present key findings from the quantitative and qualitative analyses.

Table 4. Descriptive results of the survey.

Variable	Frequency (%)
Knowledge of AI	87
Occasional use of AI	38
Online model	91
Improvement in critical thinking	64

Table 5. Analysis of hypothesis tests.

Hypothesis	<i>p</i> -Value	Result
Improvement in critical thinking	0.03	Significant
Improvement in collaboration	0.05	Not significant

These tables reveal the importance of familiarity with and use of generative AI tools in improving critical thinking among college students, although no significant improvement in collaboration was found.

4.2. Results of the Survey on the Use of Generative AI Tools

As shown in Figure 4, the dominant study modality was virtual (91%), followed by remote (8%) and hybrid (1%). The data and their corresponding analysis are available for public access in the Open Data Repository.

Figure 4. Study modality.

Figure 5 delves into the respondents' knowledge of generative AI concerning questions 1, 2, and 3. A noteworthy finding is that most of the respondents fall within the age range of 20 to 35 years, suggesting a strong interest in generative AI among this demographic. This interest is supported by the fact that a significant percentage (64%) of the respondents report a high level of knowledge about generative AI, indicating a considerable degree of familiarity and understanding.

Figure 5. Category knowledge about generative AI.

Question 4 of the survey relates to the respondents’ previous use of generative AI tools (see Figure 6). The survey also explored the respondents’ experience with generative AI tools. About 63% claimed to have used these tools before in their studies. This finding suggests a significant level of familiarity with and prior exposure to this technology among the participants. This experience with generative AI tools may have influenced their perception of how they would use them in academic settings.

Figure 6. Use of generative AI tools.

Question 5 of the survey relates to understanding and using generative AI tools in the academic field. Figure 5 focuses on the “Using Generative AI Tools” category. Here, we see that most of the respondents (62%) rated their ability to explain the concept of generative AI as medium or high. This study indicates a generally satisfactory understanding of the technology. Additionally, 60% of respondents reported using generative AI tools frequently in their academic projects. This result suggests that these tools are actively integrated into students’ learning activities.

The survey results are promising for integrating generative AI tools in classrooms. Widespread familiarity with generative AI (mentioned above) and significant prior use among respondents suggest that students are ready to leverage these tools for a better learning experience.

Data from the “Use of generative AI Tools” category reinforce this notion. The respondents showed an adequate understanding of and actively used these tools, which could produce positive results. This familiarity could positively influence collaboration on academic projects and the development of critical skills.

The study also identified generative AI tools that were popular among the participants. Figure 7 details these, with Canva being the most used (33%), followed by Chat PDF (26%), You.com (24%), ChatGPT (17%), and Tome AI (1%). It is important to note that these statistics likely reflect student usage, not educator adoption.

Figure 7. Summarizes the generative AI most frequently utilized by students.

By analyzing the most used generative AI tools, we can gain insight into how students are developing critical thinking skills and practicing collaboration. This study suggests active involvement in problem solving, idea development, and effective communication.

Questions 7, 8, 9, and 10, shown in Figure 8, focus on the “Impact on critical thinking” category. They reveal a positive result: most of the respondents (64%) believe using generative AI tools significantly improves their ability to analyze and think critically. Furthermore, most respondents perceive that these tools promote a deeper understanding of the topics studied, suggesting an overall positive impact on learning.

Figure 8. Summarizes the impact on the critical thinking category.

Questions 11, 12, 13, and 14, related to the impact on research and collaboration, shown in Figure 9, reinforce the positive impact of generative AI tools. Here, we see that most of the respondents believe these tools can significantly improve their ability to identify and evaluate relevant information in academic projects; 62% reported a significant improvement. This study suggests better research and critical thinking skills.

Figure 9. Summarizes the category of collaborative work.

Additionally, a significant % of respondents (60%) are motivated to collaborate with their colleagues using generative AI tools, positively impacting teamwork and potentially leading to a more engaging learning experience.

Questions 15 and 16, related to students’ perceptions and recommendations, shown in Figure 10, offer a positive perspective on generative AI tools in education. Most of the respondents have a favorable or neutral perception (60% favorable), which suggests a general openness to their use. Furthermore, a significant portion (59%) would frequently or consistently recommend these tools to other students. This analysis indicates strong support for the potential of generative AI to improve the learning experience.

Figure 10. Summarizes the general perception category.

Data suggest that generative AI tools have a positive impact on college students. The tools benefit students’ analytical skills, critical thinking, collaborative work, and overall perception of their college education. This study indicates significant potential to improve learning experiences.

Figure 11 shows that questions 18 and 19 delve into students’ expectations and suggestions regarding generative AI tools in collaborative learning. Interestingly, most respondents had moderate to high expectations before using these tools, and a significant percentage (64%) came in with very high expectations. The various suggestions in their answers further support this behavior. These suggestions highlight the need for frequent training in new trends and the value of these tools in improving writing activities and university work in general.

Figure 13. Keyword analysis on opinions about generative AI tools.

As in the previous analysis, the most frequent words provide valuable information. Words like “tools” (10 times) and “AI” (8 times) reinforce the focus on technology, while “good” (9 times) and “helped” (5 times) highlight the positive aspects of these tools. The students seem to emphasize how generative AI tools have helped them learn.

While the study identified promising potential for generative AI tools in education, some limitations are worth considering. First, the sample size was limited, meaning the findings may not fully represent the students’ experiences across different academic disciplines and educational levels. Second, the study was primarily based on quantitative data collected through surveys. This approach may not have captured students’ profound experiences and perceptions of these tools.

Future research could benefit from incorporating qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups. These methods would allow researchers to gain deeper insights into students’ perspectives and provide a complete understanding of how generative AI tools can be better integrated into various learning environments.

5. Discussion

The limited sample size and its specific context may not fully represent the students’ experiences in different academic disciplines and educational levels. This limitation restricts the generalization of the results to a broader population [17]. Therefore, it is essential to expand the sample in future studies to include more balanced gender representation and a greater diversity of disciplines and educational levels. This would allow for a more complete and representative view of the impact of generative AI tools in higher education [19].

Additionally, many studies, including this one, lack longitudinal data evaluating the long-term impact of generative AI tools on student outcomes. Continuous monitoring is necessary to understand how these tools affect the development of critical thinking and collaboration over time [25]. Implementing long-term studies will allow us to evaluate the sustained impact of these tools and provide a more solid basis for their integration into the educational curriculum.

Using generative AI tools raises ethical concerns, including potential algorithmic bias and data privacy. Students and educators must receive adequate training to use these technologies effectively and ethically, critically evaluating the information generated by these tools [16]. To address these concerns, it is necessary to conduct regular assessments to identify and mitigate potential biases in AI algorithms, promoting fairness and transparency.

Ongoing training and technical support are critical to effectively adopting generative AI tools. Without adequate support, students may face difficulties using these tools optimally, which may limit their potential benefits. Providing training and ongoing technical support for students and educators ensures the practical and ethical use of AI technologies, enhancing their educational impact.

For future studies, we suggest implementing several strategies. First, the sample should be expanded to include a more balanced gender representation and a greater diversity of disciplines and educational levels [18]. Second, long-term studies should be implemented to evaluate the sustained impact of generative AI tools on critical thinking and collaboration [6]. Third, training and ongoing technical support should be provided for students and educators, ensuring the effective and ethical use of AI technologies. Fourth, regular evaluations should be conducted to identify and mitigate potential biases in AI algorithms, promoting fairness and transparency [35]. Finally, generative AI tools should be systematically integrated into the educational curriculum, focusing on activities that promote critical analysis, idea generation, and effective communication [15].

With these actions and considerations, this scientific article strengthens the validity and relevance of the findings, providing a more detailed analysis of the impact of generative AI tools in higher education. These recommendations not only improve the robustness of the study but also guide future research toward a deeper and more balanced understanding of the potential of AI technologies in educational contexts.

Integrating traditional pedagogical methods with generative AI tools presents a promising advance in university education [7]. This approach aligns with the need to address the changing needs of students with innovative solutions that address cognitive challenges and improve learning experiences [18]. The discussion highlights the potential of generative AI tools to improve collaboration and critical thinking. Combining these tools with established strategies such as problem-based learning and online discussions aligns with the findings of a work that emphasizes the importance of active learning for more profound understanding [35].

Although the survey results were mixed regarding collaboration, they reflect findings from previous studies suggesting that effective implementation and resolution of technical challenges are crucial to successful collaborative learning with technology [19]. The positive impact of generative AI tools on critical thinking aligns with research indicating that these tools can improve students' ability to analyze information with innovative approaches in teacher education [15].

The discussion appropriately recognizes the importance of addressing challenges such as students' comfort with technology, specific generative AI tools, and the learning environment [7]. This study aligns with work that emphasizes carefully selecting tools and training for educators and students.

Ethical considerations around plagiarism, bias, and privacy are critical. The responsible integration of generative AI tools requires educators to promote information literacy skills and be aware of potential biases within algorithms [17]. Generative AI tools offer promising opportunities to improve collaboration and critical thinking among higher education students. However, maximizing their benefits and minimizing risks require careful implementation strategies [25].

Combining traditional teaching methodologies with generative AI tools represents an innovative approach to contemporary university education. Using ChatGPT to generate reflective questions and YOU.COM to summarize academic content, students can effectively address cognitive challenges and improve critical thinking skills within problem-based or cooperative learning frameworks [19].

It is important to note that although the survey provides valuable information, its results are not necessarily applicable to the entire student population. More research is needed to understand the full impact of generative AI tools in higher education.

Integrating generative AI tools into university educational environments can improve student collaboration and critical thinking. Our study revealed positive perceptions among

participants, indicating prior knowledge and experience with these technologies. Participants recognized the positive impact of generative AI tools in improving critical thinking skills and facilitating collaborative work.

By carefully leveraging generative AI tools and addressing identified challenges, educators can create valuable micro-curricular activities that promote critical thinking and collaborative work, preparing students for the demands of the digital age. As highlighted in the discussion, continuous evaluation and training are essential to maximize the positive impact of generative AI tools in higher education.

6. Conclusions

After a comparative analysis of several generative artificial intelligence tools, it was determined that real-time collaboration capabilities, such as simultaneous document editing and instant communication between users, are particularly effective in fostering collaborative work in educational environments. In addition, tools that provide intelligent suggestions, contextual feedback, and diverse and personalized content generation were found to be the most effective in stimulating critical thinking in students. Therefore, using tools that integrate these features is recommended to effectively promote teamwork and the development of critical thinking in the university educational context.

Our study has shown that integrating generative artificial intelligence tools in higher education significantly impacts the development of students' critical thinking. The results support our initial hypothesis, showing that using these tools facilitate students' reflections on and analysis and evaluation of information. Incorporating didactic and pedagogical strategies, including generative AI tools, has promoted more profound and reflective critical thinking.

Our study also reveals that generative artificial intelligence tools positively promote collaboration among university students. The results support our second hypothesis, showing that these tools facilitate student communication, coordination, and teamwork. The possibility of using tools such as chatbots, content generators, or collaborative platforms has improved interaction among students, fostering collaboration on academic projects and joint problem solving.

Our findings indicate that implementing didactic and pedagogical strategies integrating generative artificial intelligence tools significantly improves students' critical thinking and collaboration in university environments. Combining these tools with traditional pedagogical approaches effectively motivates students, encourages active participation, and improves learning quality. These results support our third hypothesis and suggest that the effective integration of generative AI tools in higher education can improve the educational experience of students.

Future research will include longitudinal studies to evaluate the lasting effects of generative AI tools on students' collaboration and critical thinking skills. Exploring diverse student experiences and perceptions will provide ideas for effectively integrating these tools into diverse learning contexts.

A thorough examination of the ethical considerations and potential biases associated with using generative AI tools in education is crucial. Collaboration with industry partners and educational institutions will be essential to developing and evaluating new generative AI tools designed to meet the specific needs of university students and educators.

Integrating generative AI tools into higher education can transform pedagogical strategies and significantly improve student outcomes. To maximize these benefits, it is necessary to provide ongoing essential training and adequate technical support and to develop policies that promote these technologies' ethical and responsible use. Educators and policymakers have a crucial role in effectively implementing these tools, ensuring they are used to enrich learning and prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century.

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